

A dynamic importance function for accidental scenarios generation by RESTART in the computational risk assessment of cyber-physical infrastructures

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Cyber-physical system
Risk assessment
Rare event simulation
RESTART
Black-box modelling
Grey-box modelling
Integrated power and telecommunication infrastructure

ABSTRACT

The Computational Risk Assessment (CRA) of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) calls for the analysis of accidental scenarios emerging from the complexities and interdependencies typical of CPSs. Generating these scenarios via crude Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) is impractical due to the high computational demand of simulation codes of CPSs, considering the combinatorial number of possible scenarios. In this paper, we tailor the use of Repetitive Simulation Trials After Reaching Thresholds (RESTART), a rare-event simulation method of literature, to efficiently generate relevant accidental scenarios. The tailored RESTART is guided by a dynamic Importance Function (IF) originally introduced here to dynamically characterize the relevance of the scenarios with reference to the current topology of the CPS and the susceptibility of its components. Two case studies of increasing complexity are considered: a single power grid and a CPS consisting of an Integrated Power and Telecommunication (IP&TLC) infrastructure. Results show that RESTART mines out more relevant scenarios than crude MCS for a number of different IFs based on vulnerability metrics of literature, and thus particularly efficiently when the novel IF is adopted.

1. Introduction

Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) integrate cyber and physical networks of components to enhance the performance and robustness of lifelines, such as energy, communication, transportation, and water supply [7,39]. However, the integration of the cyber and physical elements creates complex interdependencies that can shadow hazards and threats: this renders risk assessment for these systems a challenge [7,23].

With the continuous rise of computational power, Computational Risk Assessment (CRA) has established itself as an approach to generate and analyze multiple scenarios of response of complex systems and infrastructures [14,31]. With regards to CPS risk assessment, CRA can be embraced to generate and analyze multiple CPS responses to disruptive events of cyber-attacks and/or physical failures. The set of scenarios generated is to be post-processed to identify causes and criticalities for the loss of CPS functionality that would be difficult to discover by expert judgment or by traditional risk assessment methods, given the complexity of the CPS and the interdependent dynamics therein [14].

Given the random character of disruptions to CPSs, Monte Carlo

Simulation (MCS) [38] stands as the straightforward way to generate scenarios. However, the large number of scenarios required to comprehensively analyze the CPS response under the combinatorial number of disrupted elements in the system makes MCS impractical. This is even more so when the simulation of the response of the CPS to the combinations of disrupted elements is done with a high-fidelity White-Box Model (WBM), which is computationally burdensome, and those combinations which make the CPS fail have a small probability of occurrence, i.e. it is a rare-event problem [3,14]. With respect to the former issue of computationally demanding simulations, it is known that data-driven Black-Box Models (BBMs) of Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be trained to give the system responses with a good level of accuracy (if enough data are available for training) and do so in a lower computational time than WBMs; one disadvantage, however is that BBMs lack interpretation of their output with respect to the input and the physics of the problem [27]. To alleviate this last issue, Grey-Box Models (GBMs) have been introduced to effectively merge WBMs and BBMs for exploiting the benefits of both, i.e. to reduce the computational burden and retain interpretability, at least to a certain extent [16,17,21].

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For the issue of rare event simulation, common to several applications of physics and engineering [3,6,34], methods have been developed to efficiently sample small probability events that trigger scenarios of interest [4,22]. A non-exhaustive list of rare event simulation methods is provided in Table 1; the methods listed are qualitatively compared with respect to their ability to handle:

- Curse of dimensionality;
- Dynamic processes;
- Multimodal Probability Density Functions (PDFs)
- Probability estimation convergence.

Line Sampling (LS) methods (both traditional and heuristic) are designed for dealing with steady-state processes (mainly in the structural reliability domain), which makes it difficult to use for CPS applications. As for Importance Sampling (IS) (i.e., classical, state-dependent and Cross-Entropy (CE)) methods, their performance drops with the curse of dimensionality. Splitting methods, such as multilevel splitting, Subset Simulation (SS) coupled with Metropolis-Hastings sampling or IS, and the Repetitive Simulation Trials After Reaching Thresholds (RESTART), stand out for the purposes of simulating CPS responses to disturbed states, due to their capability of dealing with the curse of dimensionality, dynamic processes and multimodal PDFs, while converging relatively fast to the rare event probability estimate. Among these, RESTART has been chosen because already successfully applied for the study of interdependent and hybrid dynamic systems, for example in [20,34,35], that very much resonate with the peculiarities of CPSs, and because does not require for the identification of minimal cut sets to be used, that would result impractical when dealing with CPSs [12]. Still, RESTART needs a specific definition of the splitting process for the CPS response simulation.

The goal of this work is to tailor RESTART for efficiently guiding the exploration of accidental scenarios in a CPS, initiated by disrupted states of some of its elements. We achieve this by resorting to a novel dynamic IF that quantifies the CPS vulnerability during each simulated scenario by accounting simultaneously for (a) the centrality of CPS components exposed to the hazards/threats that can cause their disruption/failure and (b) their time-dependent susceptibility to disruption/failure. RESTART is wrapped around a general stochastic discrete-time state-space model of the CPS to track its underlying process variables and the disrupted states of its components. The introduced IF will be shown to allow RESTART to effectively allocate computational time for simulating scenarios contributing to reaching the CPS failed state, i.e., by the use of a metric of exploration efficiency. A comparison to traditional MCS and to RESTART guided by other IFs based on vulnerability metrics of literature shows that the method proposed in this paper indeed yields

better exploration efficiency.

Centrality metrics are built into the IF for guiding RESTART because they provide a quantitative indication of the importance of the CPS components with reference to the CPS network topology [10,15,28,41]. For the purposes of the present work, the centrality metric used is the Current-Flow Betweenness Centrality (CF-BC), which ranks the components with respect to their topological relevance in fulfilling the system function [25]. The original IF defined in this work also accounts for the susceptibility to failure of the components of the CPS by considering the dynamically evolving stress on the components throughout the scenario evolution to measure to what extent the component is endangered to failure while exposed to a hazard/threat. By coupling centrality and susceptibility in the IF of RESTART, the algorithm can be guided to generate relevant combinations of failures of central and susceptible components.

The performance of the method developed is benchmarked on two case studies of increasing system complexity: the IEE14 power grid [8] and an Integrated-Power and Telecommunication (IP&TLC) that couples the IEEE14 power grid with a Telecommunication Network (TLCN) [13]. The results of both cases show that the proposed methods outperform others of literature in terms of effectiveness of relevant scenarios exploration and computational savings.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 recalls the RESTART method, introduces the tailoring of RESTART to generate relevant scenarios for CPSs, and defines the novel IF. Section 3 presents the case studies and discusses the main findings. Finally, Section 4 concludes the work and suggests future research.

2. Scenario generation by RESTART

CPSs are designed and manufactured to be reliable, hence their failures are rare events. To efficiently perform the CRA of CPSs, scenarios that lead them to failure must be efficiently simulated. The simulation can be, in general terms, based on stochastic process modeling, e.g., discrete-time state-space models.

2.1. CPS state-space model

In practice, to each instant k corresponds a time $t_k = \Delta t \cdot k + t_0$, with Δt being a fixed time step and t_0 the initial time. At any discrete instant $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, the CPS state vector is $\mathbf{X}(k) \in \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $1 \leq n_x$, with initial condition $\mathbf{X}(0) = \mathbf{X}_0$. This vector contains the dynamic process variables that characterize the state of all the N interacting components in the CPS. In general terms, $\mathbf{X}(k)$ might comprise continuous and discrete variables: in our case, continuous variables are physical quantities represented by the vector $\mathbf{A}(k)$ and discrete variables are binary component

Table 1
Summary of rare events simulation methods.

Family	Method	Curse of dimensionality	Dynamic processes	Multimodal PDFs	Convergence	References
Crude Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS)	Crude MCS	●●●	Yes	●●●	●∞	[38]
Importance Sampling (IS)	Classical IS	●∞	Yes	●●○	●●○	[22]
	State-dependent IS	●∞	Yes	●●○	●●●	[29]
	Cross Entropy (CE) Method	●∞	Yes	●●○	●●●	[5]
Splitting	Multilevel splitting	●●○	Yes	●●●	●●●	[18]
	Subset Simulation (SS)	●●○	Yes	●●●	●●●	[2,26]
	Repetitive Simulation Trials After Reaching Thresholds (RESTART)	●●○	Yes	●●●	●●●	[34,37]
	Line Sampling (LS)	Traditional	●●○	No	●●○	●●○
	Heuristic	●●○	No	●●○	●●●	[9]

Legend: ineffective (●○), sufficient (●●○), or effective (●●●)

states, i.e., 1 (“up”) or 0 (“down”), represented by the vector $\mathbf{II}(k)$, so that:

$$\mathbf{X}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}(k) \\ \mathbf{II}(k) \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

For any component $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, its multidimensional state vector $\mathbf{X}_j(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{x_j}}$, $1 \leq n_{x_j} \leq n_x$, is the portion of $\mathbf{X}(k)$ that contains the dynamic process variables of that component.

The CPS state variables evolve in time following the one-step transition process in Eq. (2) where $F(\cdot)$ is a nonlinear state-transition function that considers the N components interdependencies, $\mathbf{U}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ represents the controlled variables (e.g., power generators settings in the power grid, data packets in the telecommunication network), whereas $\mathbf{E}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_e}$ are the uncontrolled external stimuli (e.g., power demands); for each j -th component, we denote its controlled and uncontrolled variables as $\mathbf{U}_j(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{u_j}}$ and $\mathbf{E}_j(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{e_j}}$, respectively, where $n_{u_j}, n_{e_j} \geq 0$:

$$\mathbf{X}(k+1) = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}(k), \mathbf{U}(k), \mathbf{E}(k)) \quad (2)$$

The simulation of the CPS uses a co-simulation approach to account for the interactions among the N components, while avoiding dependence on the underlying models of those components. Each component is characterized by its own independent model that operates in its corresponding state-space domain. To enable the co-simulation of these diverse models, we implement the hierarchical approach described in [16], which provides a master algorithm coordinating the co-simulation process and integrating the different models. This approach requires proceeding as follows (1) organizing the CPS into layers: each layer contains the components that control those in the layer immediately below it; (2) defining physical and cyber bottom-up and top-down flows (e.g., bottom layers measurements flow up until they reach a central controller (bottom-up), where control inputs are computed and, then, sent to the bottom layer components (top-down)); (3) simulating at each time k the dynamical response of the CPS using Algorithm 1. This procedure yields a detailed simulation of the CPS response at the end of each time window (t_k, t_{k+1}) , $k \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$.

2.2. RESTART for CPS accidental scenario generation

For the general CPS discrete-time state-space model introduced in the previous Section, we tailor RESTART to generate the relevant scenarios of interest. This is achieved by integrating the co-simulation framework with RESTART via the state-space model (as illustrated in Fig. 1), allowing us to identify the most relevant sequences of $\mathbf{X}(k)$ that can lead the CPS to failure. Considering this, RESTART proceeds as follows:

- 1) Define $\phi(\mathbf{X}(k))$ that is a scalar map $\phi: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ called *Importance Function* (IF), whose range is divided into $m+1$ regions defined by several thresholds $T_i \in \mathbb{R}$, $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, such that $T_{i'} > T_i$, if and only if $i' > i$. Such thresholds define m nested regions of increasing

Algorithm 1

Procedure for the recursive evaluation of the one-step state transition function $F(\cdot)$ in the CPS state-space model (Eq. (2)) considering the hierarchical approach in [16].

Inputs:	last state $\mathbf{X}(k)$ and CPS hierarchical model
Output:	updated next state $\mathbf{X}(k+1)$
1	Sample the external stimuli values $\mathbf{E}(k)$ from assigned PDFs
2	Update the status of components $\mathbf{II}(k)$
3	Collect measurements from and states of components (bottom-up data)
4	Simulate the (imperfect) bottom-transmission
5	Use the transmitted data to compute the CPS control inputs $\mathbf{U}(k)$ (top-down data)
6	Simulate the (imperfect) top-down transmission
7	Use the transmitted data to evaluate $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}(k), \mathbf{U}(k), \mathbf{E}(k))$ (Eq. 2)
8	Return $\mathbf{X}(k+1)$

relevance $C_i := \{\mathbf{X} \in \Omega | \phi(\mathbf{X}(k)) \geq T_i\}$; by denoting $C_0 = \Omega$, then, $C_0 \supset C_1 \dots \supset C_m$, and the intermediate regions $\Delta C_i := C_i - C_{i+1}$ for $i \in \{0, \dots, m-1\}$, and $\Delta C_m = C_m$.

- 2) Run a main trial, which is a crude MCS of $\mathbf{X}(k)$, track $\phi(\mathbf{X}(k))$ and record the instant(s) it up-crosses the threshold T_1 ; label the up-crossing event(s) as U_1 and the occurrence instants(s) as k_{U_1} , and save the corresponding state(s) $\mathbf{X}(k_{U_1})$.
- 3) For each U_1 , perform $R_1 - 1$, $R_1 \in \mathbb{N}$, simulations called *retrials* starting from k_{U_1} with initial condition $\mathbf{X}(k_{U_1})$ and finishing at some end-of-simulation condition (e.g., mission time, occurrence of a fixed number of events) or when $\phi(\mathbf{X}(k))$ down-crosses T_1 ; label the latter event as D_1 .
- 4) If during any of the R_1 retrials $\phi(\mathbf{X}(k))$ up-crosses the threshold $T_2 > T_1$, steps 2) and 3) are repeated for labelled event(s) U_2 , instants k_{U_2} and states $\mathbf{X}(k_{U_2})$ are saved, and $R_2 - 1$, $R_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, new retrials are simulated for each U_2 , until the end-of-simulation condition is reached or T_2 is down-crossed.
- 5) Repeat steps 2) to 5) for all remaining thresholds and retrials, or until the end-of-simulation condition is reached, i.e., simulate $R_i - 1$ new retrials, $R_i \in \mathbb{N}$, when $\phi(\mathbf{X}(k))$ up-crosses any threshold T_i . If $\phi(\cdot)$ goes above several thresholds at once, say $\{T_i, T_{i+1}, \dots, T_{i+b}\}$ or b thresholds above T_i at once, then run $\prod_{i=i}^{i+b} (R_i - 1)$ retrials (i.e. a number equal to the product of the retrials that should be run for each threshold(s)).

Fig. 2a shows an example of the application of RESTART to a two-dimensional process $\mathbf{X}(k) = (x_1(k), x_2(k))^T$, whereas Fig. 2b shows the corresponding mapping $\phi(\mathbf{X}(k))$. The rationale of RESTART is that it is more likely for a state $\mathbf{X}(k)$ to reach an intermediate region when it transitions from a state in a region of immediately lower importance, rather than jumping abruptly across several regions. Therefore, by oversampling states within high-importance regions, the likelihood of observing states of even greater importance increases. This goal is primarily achieved if $\phi(\cdot)$ effectively highlights relevant rare states, ultimately enabling RESTART to allocate the computational effort to simulating low probability events.

As highlighted in [36], the definition of the IF in step 1) is most critical for a successful implementation of RESTART. An effective IF should:

- Assign low importance values to high probability states;
- Provide similar importance values to states nearby a threshold;
- Reduce importance skipping, i.e., sudden IF jumps across several regions.

Typical IFs adopted for the analysis of various complex systems are briefly discussed hereafter. In [20], the number of line outages is taken as IF to guide the simulation, but it is limited to dealing with static states and conditions of power grid components. In [35,34], the cut sets of a system, found from its structure function, are used as IF to guide the sampling by RESTART; however, cut sets identification in large CPS is difficult, if not impossible [11,12]. CPS vulnerability metrics, such as Energy Not Supplied (ENS) or System Average Interruption Frequency Index (SAIFI), can be used as IFs given that they offer a synthetic characterization of disruptive CPS scenarios [13]; however, the cumulated information that they provide is strictly conditioned to the occurrence of the rare failure events so that if no failure occurs, such metrics do not provide any useful information (e.g., they are zero throughout the simulation) and RESTART would act as crude MCS.

In this work, we introduce an original IF specific for the CRA of CPSs. Based on the centrality and susceptibility metrics of all the components of the CPS, we compute throughout the simulation its *Dynamic Network-level Vulnerability* (DNV) to measure the level of exposition to failure of the CPS and allocate the computational effort primarily to the system vulnerabilities to probabilistically favor the occurrence of CPS failures.

Fig. 1. Integration of the master co-simulator [16] with RESTART.

Fig. 2. Visualization of RESTART for a two-dimensional state: in (a), the process evolves in the state-space domain, which is mapped simultaneously into the IF domain in (b), where new retrials emerge when the IF surpasses some threshold.

For more detailed insights and examples on centrality and susceptibility metrics, please refer to [Appendix A](#).

As mentioned in the Introduction, *centrality* is a concept used in network analysis to describe the influence that the single elements of a network have on its performance [15]. Since CPS are flow networks (e.g. flows of electricity, packets or substances among the multiple components), a suitable centrality metric is the Current Flow Betweenness Centrality (CF-BC) [25]. This metric characterizes the importance of a component based on the average topology-induced flow passing through it, defined as follows. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph of the CPS, with V being the set of the n_V vertices (e.g., components) and E the n_E edges (e.g., interconnections) of the network, so that the total number of network elements is $n_V + n_E$. Given the sets of sources $S \subseteq V$ and targets $T \subseteq V$, the CF-BC of a j -th node is:

$$c_j := \frac{\sum_{\{s<t\}} I_j^{(s-t)}}{(1/2)n_V(n_V - 1)}, \quad (3)$$

where $I_j^{(s-t)}$ is the flow due to a source-target pair of components $s - t$, $s \in S$ and $t \in T$. We normalize all the centrality values by the maximum obtained centrality to ensure $c_j \in [0, 1]$, for any component j . Notice that this metric provides us with a ranking of the components that is source-target dependent; thus, by choosing the $s - t$ pairs, we can tune the exploration to focus on the accidental scenarios for a particular set of components.

The other quantity used to build the IF is the *susceptibility* of a component, which quantifies at any instant k its usage level (or, vice versa, its resourcefulness) with respect to design specifications and ratings, i.e., the stress when exposed to hazards/threats. Thus, a value of susceptibility equal to zero indicates “no usage” or “up” (i.e., resourceful component), whereas a value equal to one corresponds to “full usage” or “down” (i.e., resourceless component). Since each j -th component is

characterized by its state vector $\mathbf{X}_j(k)$, we define its susceptibility $s_j(k) \in [0, 1]$ by considering that the l -th state variable in $\mathbf{X}_j(k)$ has a maximum factory rating $x_j^{+(l)}$ that cannot be exceeded (the definition for minimum ratings is dually equivalent):

$$s_j(k) := \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{X}_j^{(l)}(k)}{x_j^{+(l)}} & \text{if } j \text{ is operating;} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In line with [36], we combine the centrality in Eq. (3) with the susceptibility in Eq. (4) to provide a *weighted susceptibility* (Eq. (5)) that emphasizes the role of components that contribute to the vulnerability of the system when they are susceptible (closer to the limit $x_j^{+(l)}$):

$$v_j(k) := c_j \cdot s_j(k). \quad (5)$$

We, then, obtain the DNV metric $\mathbb{V}(k)$ as the sum of the weighted susceptibilities of all components in the network:

$$\mathbb{V}(k) = \sum_{j=1}^{n_N+n_E} c_j \cdot s_j(k) = \sum_{j=1}^{n_N+n_E} v_j(k) \quad (6)$$

In practice, the dynamic network-level vulnerability $\mathbb{V}(k)$ of the CPS can be obtained as shown in Fig. 3 by:

- 1) modeling the CPS by means of the state vector $\mathbf{X}(k)$ and its dynamics as in Eq. (2);
- 2) mapping the CPS into a graph $G = (V, E)$, where vertices V are components (e.g., bar buses, generators, electrical loads, TLC gateways, controller units), and the edges E are interconnections (e.g., transmission lines, transformers, fiber-optic cables);

Fig. 3. Steps for the calculation of the DNLV of a generic network.

- 3) calculating the CF-BC for all the elements in G with Eq. (3), where the $(s-t)$ pairs are defined by the sources S that inject flows (e.g., generators, control center) and the targets T that receive flows (e.g., customers);
- 4) computing, throughout the simulation, the susceptibility (Eq. (4)) and the weighted susceptibility (Eq. (5)) of each component, to obtain the DNLV (Eq. (6)).

2.3. Performance metric

For any scenario generation method \mathcal{M} that produces n_{sim} simulation points in a dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{M}} = \{\mathbf{X}_{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{(n_{\text{sim}})}\}$, we can determine the exploration efficiency $\xi_{\phi}(T)$ of an IF ϕ ; this metric computes the ratio between the number points in $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{M}}$ that fall within a generic importance region ΔC (defined by a generic threshold T in the range of ϕ) over the

total number points n_{sim} :

$$\xi_\phi(T) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{n_{\text{sim}}} [\phi(\mathbf{X}_{(n)}) > T]}{n_{\text{sim}}}, \quad (7)$$

where the Iverson bracket $[\cdot]$ counts one when $\phi(\mathbf{X}_{(n)}(k)) > T$ is true or zero otherwise. The ξ_ϕ is then representative of the conditional probability associated to the region from T onward.

An effective IF ϕ , alongside its thresholds $\{T_0, T_1, \dots, T_m\}$, can be recognized through the values of ξ_ϕ , calculated over some given (generated) dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{M}}$. A consistent decrease in ξ_ϕ , as thresholds increase, indicates a balanced probability of transitioning between importance zones: in RESTART, this pattern suggests a reduced skipping and smooth threshold crossings, allowing ϕ , in combination with the strategic over-sampling of importance regions, to produce a balanced acceleration of relevant rare events occurrences while encouraging exploration of the state-space domain. In practice, a quasi-optimal thresholds setting by fixed number yields a balanced probability of transitioning between importance zones, i.e., equal conditional probabilities of transitioning from each region C_i to C_{i+1} . In other words, being m the number of thresholds, a balanced probability of transitioning between importance zones occurs when ξ_ϕ decreases by $1/(m+1)$ for each threshold increase [37]. Considering an alternative IF ϕ' with different thresholds $\{T'_0, T'_1, T'_2, \dots\}$ (defined in the range of ϕ), we can claim its superiority if $\xi_{\phi'}(T'_i) > \xi_\phi(T_i)$ over $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{M}}$, for any $i \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$: this means that ϕ' detects events of low probability (high importance) more often than ϕ by enabling the over-sampling of those events not detected by ϕ .

3. Case studies

This Section presents two case studies. In Section 3.1, we consider the IEEE14 power grid case [8] with a centralized controller. For the CRA of this system, RESTART is guided by the DNLV and traditional CPS vulnerability metrics (Power Generation Mismatch (PGM), number of down components, and Energy Not Supplied (ENS)) and the simulation performance is compared with a crude MCS. In Section 3.2, we consider an IP&TLC CPS [13], where data transmission between the power grid and the centralized controller is affected by the TLC; in this case, we compare the performance of crude MCS and RESTART guided by the DNLV. In both case studies, models and procedures are implemented in Python, where Pandapower [33] is used for power flow calculations and NetworkX [19] for graph calculations. Simulations are performed on Windows 11 on an Intel i7 9750H computer at 2.2 GHz.

3.1. IEEE14 power grid

The IEEE14 power grid [8] is composed of 14 buses, denoted by \mathcal{B} ,

which interconnect multiple electrical components: \mathcal{C} the 11 electrical loads (customers) that demand active and reactive power, \mathcal{G} the 2 controllable generators that input active and reactive power plus 3 synchronous condensers modelled as generators with zero active power inputs, \mathcal{L} the 20 transmission lines that interconnect the buses, and \mathcal{T} the 3 transformers that separate high and low voltage zones (Fig. 4a).

Each component of the power grid is equipped with a Smart Monitoring Device (SMD) (e.g., a Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU)) that monitors, at each instant k , the component availability and collects electrical measurements. The SMDs send these values to a Control Center (CC) that computes control inputs for the generators by solving an Alternating Current Optimal Power Flow (AC-OPF) problem with the parameters described in [24]; such control inputs are, then, passed to the power grid generators. Without loss of generality, we use a Power Flow (PF) model to obtain the detailed power grid response, enabling the simulation of the hierarchical closed-loop control shown in Fig. 4b. For the PF and the OPF, the slack bus is the available generator with the highest active power rating at instant k .

The vectors $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_d(k) = (\bar{p}_{d,1}(k), \dots, \bar{p}_{d,11}(k))^T$ and $\bar{\mathbf{q}}_d(k) = (\bar{q}_{d,1}(k), \dots, \bar{q}_{d,11}(k))^T$ group the active and reactive power demands of all the customers at any instant k , respectively, defining the demands of each customer $j \in \mathcal{C}$. The power grid uncontrolled inputs vector (i.e., external stimuli) $\mathbf{E}_{\text{PG}}(k)$ is, thus, the concatenation of the active and reactive power demand vectors:

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{PG}}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{p}}_d(k) \\ \bar{\mathbf{q}}_d(k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{22} \quad (8)$$

The values of $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_d(k)$ and $\bar{\mathbf{q}}_d(k)$ are taken from [13], consisting of 30 days of historical open data provided by [32], sampled every $\Delta t = 15$ [min]. For generalization purposes, we process the Terna data by applying min-max normalization and, then, multiplying the results by the nominal active and reactive power load demands of each customer in the IEEE14 case.

The binary statuses of components are tracked at any instant k by the vectors $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{Gen}}(k)$, $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{Line}}(k)$, and $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{Trafo}}(k)$ for generators, transmission lines and transformers, respectively. We place them in the binary status vector $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_{\text{PG}}(k)$ (Eq. (9)), for which we consider that generators \mathcal{G} , transmission lines \mathcal{L} , and transformers \mathcal{T} can fail and be repaired with the exponential rates in Table 2, making $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_{\text{PG}}(k)$ follow a binary Markov chain with an initial condition $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_{\text{PG}}(0) = \mathbf{1}$ (all components are up):

$$\boldsymbol{\Pi}_{\text{PG}}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{Gen}}(k) \\ \boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{Line}}(k) \\ \boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{Trafo}}(k) \end{pmatrix} \in \{0, 1\}^{28} \quad (9)$$

The CC receives at each instant k both $\mathbf{E}_{\text{PG}}(k)$ and $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_{\text{PG}}(k)$ to create

Fig. 4. Visualization of the controlled IEEE14 power grid case. In (a), the power grid schematic diagram and in (b) the hierarchical control scheme.

Table 2
Power grid failure and repair rates [13].

Component	$\lambda_{\text{Rep}} [h^{-1}]$	$\lambda_{\text{Fail}} [h^{-1}]$
Generator	24	3e-3
Transmission Line	12	3.5e-3
Transformer	4	19e-3

and solve an instance of the AC-OPF, returning in output the power grid controlled inputs $\mathbf{U}_{\text{PG}}(k)$, i.e., the voltage angles $\mathbf{v}_{\perp, \text{gen}}(k)$, active power generation $\mathbf{p}_{\text{g, gen}}(k)$ and voltage magnitudes $\mathbf{v}_{\text{m, gen}}(k)$ of controlled generators, and the voltages magnitude $\mathbf{v}_{\text{m, sc}}(k)$ setpoints of the synchronous condensers:

$$\mathbf{U}_{\text{PG}}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{v}_{\perp, \text{gen}}(k) \\ \mathbf{p}_{\text{g, gen}}(k) \\ \mathbf{v}_{\text{m, gen}}(k) \\ \mathbf{v}_{\text{m, sc}}(k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^9 \quad (10)$$

If the AC-OPF does not converge, we set $\mathbf{U}_{\text{PG}}(k) = 0$ (i.e., request all generators to shut down).

The control inputs are fed to each generator and, then, the PF is run to obtain the detailed response of the physical quantities in the power grid $\Lambda_{\text{PG}}(k)$, made of, but not limited to: $\mathbf{p}_d(k)$ and $\mathbf{q}_d(k)$, i.e., the actual active and reactive power received by the customers, $\mathbf{p}_g(k)$ and $\mathbf{q}_g(k)$, i.e., the actual active and reactive power generations, $\mathbf{v}_m(k)$ and $\mathbf{v}_{\perp}(k)$, i.e., the voltage magnitudes and angles at each bus:

$$\Lambda_{\text{PG}}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{p}_d(k) \\ \mathbf{q}_d(k) \\ \mathbf{p}_g(k) \\ \mathbf{q}_g(k) \\ \mathbf{v}_m(k) \\ \mathbf{v}_{\perp}(k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{60} \quad (11)$$

The binary statuses $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{PG}}(k)$ (Eq. (9)) and physical quantities $\Lambda_{\text{PG}}(k)$ (Eq. (11)) are appended within the state vector of the power grid $\mathbf{X}_{\text{PG}}(k)$ (see the Λ - $\mathbf{\Pi}$ representation of Eq. (1)):

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{PG}}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_{\text{PG}}(k) \\ \mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{PG}}(k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{88} \quad (12)$$

RESTART is setup with a fixed number of retrials $R_i = 4$, for each threshold T_i , $i \in \{1, 2, \dots\}$; the number of main trials R_0 is not set, letting the scenarios generation run until $T_{\text{exec}} = 6[h]$ is reached considering a mission time representative of a week of operation $\tau_f = 100[h]$ (i.e., enough to obtain at least one hundred crude MCS scenarios for comparison). In the following, we list the IFs that are used for the comparison of the results; for consistency, we develop $m = 8$ thresholds for all IFs (Table 3).

The *Power Generation Mismatch (PGM)* (ϕ_1) computes the difference between the apparent power generated in a scenario and that of a reference normal conditions scenario. Let $\mathbf{S}(k)$ and $\bar{\mathbf{S}}(k)$ be the vectors of actual and reference complex power generations at instant k , respectively. Then, $\phi_1(k)$ is the sum of magnitudes of the apparent power

differences among all generators ($\phi_1(k) = 0$ if the actual system condition is equal to the reference one (i.e., normal conditions); $\phi_1(k) > 0$, otherwise):

$$\phi_1(k) = \sum_{j=1}^5 \left| |\mathbf{S}^{(j)}(k)| - |\bar{\mathbf{S}}^{(j)}(k)| \right| \quad (13)$$

Thresholds (Table 3, 1st row) are defined by, first, sorting in ascending order the maximum active power ratings of the PV generators (i.e., $\{140.0, 332.4\}$ [MW]): each of these ratings are one threshold. Next, we consider a temporary last threshold equal to the sum of the ratings (i.e., 472.4 [MW]); in-between these thresholds, we insert two more thresholds quadratically distanced from the one previously added. Finally, we remove the temporary last threshold.

The *number of down components* (ϕ_2) counts the number of unavailable components in the power grid at each instant k :

$$\phi_2(k) = 28 - \sum_{j=1}^{28} \mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{PG}}^{(j)}(k) \quad (14)$$

Thresholds (Table 3, 2nd row) are set equal to integer values starting from zero, which are the values that $\phi_2(k)$ can take.

The *ENS percentage* (ϕ_3) computes at each instant k the accumulated portion of active power not delivered to each customer $j \in \mathcal{C}$:

$$\phi_3(k) = \frac{1}{11} \sum_{j=1}^{11} \left(1 - \frac{p_{dj}(k)}{\bar{p}_{dj}(k)} \right) \quad (15)$$

Thresholds (Table 3, 3rd row) are set considering that if a single customer does not receive any active power, ϕ_3 increments by $1/11 \approx 0.091$; for a half demand lost, the increment is $1/22 \approx 0.045$: we use this value to create the thresholds in an incremental manner.

The *Dynamic Network-Level Vulnerability* (ϕ_4) is that defined in Section 2 (see Eq. (6)). We compute the CF-BC considering that sources are the controllable generators in \mathcal{S} (i.e., we drop synchronous condensers) and targets are all the customers in \mathcal{C} . Thresholds (Table 3, 4th row) are constructed by first obtaining the sum of all centralities, i.e., 11.091. For the first threshold, we consider that all components operate normally around 18% of their capacity (i.e., a base susceptibility of 0.18), yielding an average DNLV of 1.99: this is the first threshold. We repeat the procedure considering components operating at 90% of their capacity, yielding a DNLV of 9.98: this is the last threshold. The remaining thresholds are inserted in between, distanced quadratically from the one previously inserted.

We compute the exploration efficiency ξ_{ϕ} of each ϕ (see Section 2.3) over the generated datasets to compare the performance of the scenario generation methods, considering, without loss of generality, the two lowest thresholds $T_i^{\phi} = \{T_1^{\phi}, T_2^{\phi}\}$ associated to each ϕ (i.e., the two highest probability regions). In Table 4, each row summarizes the results for a specific scenario generation method, along with the total number of simulation points produced by this procedure (n_{sim}). In the columns, we report (1) the exploration efficiency of the IF used in that procedure (underlined), and (2) the exploration efficiency of the other IFs with their corresponding thresholds calculated over the simulation points of that procedure, highlighting in bold those with the highest exploration efficiency. This comparison allows us to evaluate the effectiveness of the different IFs sample relevant configurations and generate correspondingly relevant scenarios.

When MCS is used (Table 4, row 1), $\xi_{\phi}(T_1^{\phi})$ is noticeably larger than $\xi_{\phi}(T_2^{\phi})$ for any ϕ , implying that MCS always allocates more computational resources than DNV into simulating high probability scenarios below the first threshold, which are irrelevant, i.e., normal conditions or failure events that do not alter the power grid normal conditions. This is evident for the ENS ϕ_3 , which is equal to zero (row 1, columns 7 and 8), meaning that the simulations never explore scenarios in which

Table 3
Threshold values considered for each IF.

IF	Thresholds
ϕ_1	{15.55, 62.22, 140.00, 161.37, 225.51, 332.40, 347.95, 394.62}
ϕ_2	{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8}
ϕ_3	{0.04, 0.09, 0.13, 0.18, 0.22, 0.27, 0.31, 0.36}
ϕ_4	{1.99, 2.15, 2.64, 3.46, 4.60, 6.07, 7.86, 9.98}

Table 4
Performance comparison between MCS and RESTART for the IEEE14 case.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
		ϕ_1			ϕ_2			ϕ_3	ϕ_4	
Method	n_{sim}	$\xi_{\phi_1}(T_1^{\phi_1})$	$\xi_{\phi_1}(T_2^{\phi_1})$	$\xi_{\phi_2}(T_1^{\phi_2})$	$\xi_{\phi_2}(T_2^{\phi_2})$	$\xi_{\phi_3}(T_1^{\phi_3})$	$\xi_{\phi_3}(T_2^{\phi_3})$	$\xi_{\phi_4}(T_1^{\phi_4})$	$\xi_{\phi_4}(T_2^{\phi_4})$	
1	MCS	40,648	0.0129	0.008	0.0653	0.0059	0.0	0.0	0.4667	0.1974
2	ϕ_1	30,280	<u>0.8327</u>	<u>0.8327</u>	0.8349	0.0375	0.0	0.0	0.9216	0.8801
3	ϕ_2	32,287	0.0662	0.0478	<u>0.3254</u>	<u>0.0548</u>	0.0	0.0	0.5246	0.3257
4	ϕ_3	32,193	0.0246	0.0148	0.0854	0.0056	<u>0.0</u>	<u>0.0</u>	0.4810	0.2136
5	ϕ_4	38,218	0.5717	0.5486	0.604	0.0467	0.0	0.0	0.9683	0.8921

customers are not supplied with energy. The noticeably larger values of $\xi_{\phi_4}(T_1^{\phi_4})$ and $\xi_{\phi_4}(T_2^{\phi_4})$ imply that the DNV detects low importance zones more often than MCS; indeed, more than half of the simulation points generated using MCS are in the lowest importance region of ϕ_4 (i.e., below the first threshold), suggesting that this IF is more effective for scenario exploration.

When RESTART is used, the calculated ξ_{ϕ} is larger than for MCS for all IFs, except the ENS ϕ_3 , which behaves as MCS. These results suggest

that RESTART effectively generates more relevant scenarios if the used IF is suitable for this purpose. In our case, all IFs satisfy the basic requirement of assigning low importance values to high probability events (i.e., events in which the CPS operates in normal conditions), yet some of them fail to reduce skipping or assign similar importance values to states near the thresholds, as explained by the obtained exploration efficiency values. Indeed, the IF with the highest ξ_{ϕ} in its own run is the DNV ϕ_4 (row 5, column 9), where the reduction from $\xi_{\phi_4}(T_1^{\phi_4})$ to

Fig. 5. Example of disconnection of a low importance component (transmission line (6, 12)).

$\xi_{\phi_4} \left(T_2^{\phi_4} \right)$ of 0.08 (i.e., the difference between the values in columns 9 and 10, row 5) provides a reasonable setting of threshold values, enabling a balanced exploration of the importance regions (i.e., it approaches $1/9 = 0.\bar{1}$). On the other hand, ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 , and ϕ_3 show a reduced performance overall: their exploration efficiency is low when compared to the DNLV, even in their own runs, and the reduction between thresholds is either too large or too small. For ϕ_3 , the zeros in columns 7 and 8 of Table 4 mean that this IF is not capable to detect higher importance zones above the first threshold, resulting useless for guiding RESTART in scenario exploration. Such reduced performances are explained by their shared inferior properties: these IFs react to failures in the system (i.e., component disconnections that yield a suboptimal system performance), which cause discontinuous jumps of (some) process variables and, thus, importance skipping. Since the susceptibility is weighted by the centrality in the DNV, the importance skipping is reduced for the low centrality components that are, in practice, the majority of the components in the network.

We complement the above discussion with a visualization of the

evolution of the IFs across a simulation when components fail. Fig. 5 presents a case in which a low centrality component (i.e., transmission line (6,12)), fails between 11:00 AM and 02:30 PM, but not sufficient to cause power dispatch issues. When the failure occurs, both ϕ_1 and ϕ_4 increase little due to the low importance of this component and ϕ_2 increases by one (i.e., one device down) as expected; ϕ_3 , instead, does not provide any information about this scenario because all customers receive the demanded power. Fig. 6 repeats the experiment for a higher centrality component (i.e., transmission line (1,5)), but still not enough to cause power dispatch issues. We observe a larger increase in ϕ_1 and ϕ_4 ; however, ϕ_2 increases by one just as before, providing no information about the differences between the two scenarios and ϕ_3 , again, does not provide any information since the network is still satisfying the requested power demands. In both experiments, the ϕ_4 curves are smooth and always greater than zero, evolving accordingly with the state variables and increasing when components are more susceptible, suggesting an assignment of similar importance values to states near the thresholds. Such behavior is not observed in other IFs: as discussed above, ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 , and ϕ_3 do not provide any useful information when the

Fig. 6. Example of disconnection of a high importance component (transmission line (1,5)).

system is operating in normal conditions, but only when a failure occurs.

3.2. Integrated power and telecommunication CPS

In this case study, we consider an Integrated Power and Telecommunication Infrastructure (IP&TLC) [13] that combines the IEEE14 power grid of Section 3.1 with the Telecommunication Network (TLCN) sketched in Fig. 7a. The SMDs transmit the necessary data via the TLCN to the CC located at TLCN node 7, where the received measurements are processed to obtain the AC-OPF values to be sent back to the generators through the TLCN, enabling the hierarchical closed-loop control scheme shown in Fig. 7b.

As in Section 3.1, the power grid is affected at any instant k by uncontrolled inputs, i.e., the evolving power demands $\mathbf{E}_{PG}(k)$ (see Eq. (8)); the TLCN, instead, is not affected by external stimuli and, thus:

$$\mathbf{E}_{TLCN}(k) = \emptyset \quad (16)$$

The power grid controlled inputs $\mathbf{U}_{PG}(k)$ are the generators control settings (see Eq. (10)), and the TLCN controlled inputs $\mathbf{U}_{TLCN}(k)$ contains the packets to be delivered: the bottom-up packet $\mathbf{U}_{TLCN}^{\downarrow}(k)$ are the $\mathbf{E}_{PG}(k)$ measurements and components status $\mathbf{II}_{PG}(k)$ (Eq. (9)) collected by the SMDs, whereas the top-down packets $\mathbf{U}_{TLCN}^{\uparrow}(k)$ are the generators control settings as in the AC-OPF output:

$$\mathbf{U}_{TLCN}^{\downarrow}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{E}_{PG}(k) \\ \mathbf{II}_{PG}(k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{50}, \quad \mathbf{U}_{TLCN}^{\uparrow}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{v}_{\leftarrow, \text{gen}}(k) \\ \mathbf{p}_{g, \text{gen}}(k) \\ \mathbf{v}_{m, \text{gen}}(k) \\ \mathbf{v}_{m, \text{sc}}(k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{10} \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{U}_{TLCN}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}_{TLCN}^{\downarrow}(k) \\ \mathbf{U}_{TLCN}^{\uparrow}(k) \end{pmatrix}$$

An imperfect transmission along the TLCN might trigger packet losses, resulting in (1) incomplete data arriving at the CC, i.e., empty spaces in $\mathbf{U}_{TLCN}^{\downarrow}(k)$, or (2) failure to deliver control settings, i.e., $\mathbf{U}_{TLCN}^{\uparrow}(k)$ does not reach some generator(s). A transmission function Ψ (see Eq. (19) below) tests the success of these transmissions, which are influenced by the architecture and technology of the TLCN. We model such behaviors by adapting the approach in [13] as follows.

The TLCN is an undirected weighted graph $G = (V, E, t_d)$, where vertices V are the TLCN nodes, edges E are the TLCN links, and weights $t_d : E \times [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ assign to each edge $e \in E$ a time-evolving time delay $t_d(e, t_{\text{day}}(k))$, with $t_{\text{day}}(k) \geq 0$ the time of the day at instant k . These time delays follow a reflected Wiener process with a standard deviation σ and boundaries $t^- > 0$ and $t^+ > t^-$. Fig. 8 exemplifies this behavior for

a day of operation, considering $t^- = 30[\text{ms}]$, $t^+ = 50[\text{ms}]$, and $\sigma = 1 [\text{ms}]$. At any instant k , any node in V and edge in E might become unavailable with probability $p_d^v = 1e - 5$ and $p_d^e = 1e - 6$, respectively, due to sudden disconnections of nodes/edges or underlying TLCN protocol diversions; the binary status of nodes and links are represented by vectors $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{node}}(k)$ and $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{link}}(k)$, respectively.

For any origin-destination pair $(a, b) \in V \times V$, $a \neq b$, we compute a transmission path $\mathcal{P}_{ab} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$, $v_1 = a$ and $v_n = b$, using the TLCN adjacency matrix and the Dijkstra algorithm [30]. We mimic the process of (re)establishing network connections by caching these paths until they become disconnected (i.e., some TLC nodes or links become unavailable, yielding the established path unconnected): if that is the case, we recompute the path; however, if no path between (a, b) exists, then $\mathcal{P} = \emptyset$. Once the path is set, we compute its total time delay $T_d(\mathcal{P}_{ab}, t_{\text{day}}(k))$ as:

$$T_d(\mathcal{P}_{ab}, t_{\text{day}}(k)) = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} t_d((v_i, v_{i+1}), t_{\text{day}}(k)) & \text{if } \mathcal{P}_{ab} \neq \emptyset \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

A transmission function $\Psi(\mathbf{d}, t_{\text{day}})$ tests the transmission: if $T_d(\cdot) \leq t^{\text{max}}$, for some timeout $t^{\text{max}} > 0$, then the transmission is successful and the destination device at TLCN node b receives the packet \mathbf{d} ; otherwise, the destination receives \emptyset (empty packet):

$$\Psi(\mathbf{d}, t_{\text{day}}) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{d} & \text{if } T_d(\mathcal{P}_{ab}, t_{\text{day}}) \leq t^{\text{max}}, \\ \emptyset & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Fig. 9 exemplifies some cases in which the transmission can succeed or fail, considering $(a, b) = (6, 7)$ and $t^{\text{max}} = 80 [\text{ms}]$.

The TLCN state vector $\mathbf{X}_{TLCN}(k)$ stores at any instant k the graph variables when doing the bottom-up ($\mathbf{X}_{TLCN}^{\downarrow}(k)$) and top-down ($\mathbf{X}_{TLCN}^{\uparrow}(k)$) transmissions: time delays $\mathbf{t}_d(k)$, and binary status of nodes $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{node}}(k)$ and links $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{link}}(k)$:

$$\mathbf{X}_{TLCN}^{\downarrow}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{t}_d^{\downarrow}(k) \\ \boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{node}}^{\downarrow}(k) \\ \boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{link}}^{\downarrow}(k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{27}, \quad \mathbf{X}_{TLCN}^{\uparrow}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{t}_d^{\uparrow}(k) \\ \boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{node}}^{\uparrow}(k) \\ \boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{link}}^{\uparrow}(k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{27} \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{X}_{TLCN}(k) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{X}_{TLCN}^{\downarrow}(k) \\ \mathbf{X}_{TLCN}^{\uparrow}(k) \end{pmatrix}$$

We enable the use of RESTART for the IP&TLCN by concatenating the input and state vectors of the power grid and the TLCN (see Eqs. (8) and (16) for the external stimuli, Eqs. (10) and (17) for the controlled

Fig. 7. Description of the IP&TLCN: in (a), the topology of the TLCN; in b), the hierarchical scheme of the IP&TLCN, with the explicit bottom/up and top/down flows and uncontrollable inputs (external stimuli).

Fig. 8. Visualization of the evolution of time delays.

Fig. 9. Different scenarios of successful and unsuccessful transmission between two nodes.

inputs, and Eqs. (12) and (20) for the state vector):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}(k) &= (\mathbf{E}_{PG}^T(k), \mathbf{E}_{TLCN}^T(k))^T, \\ \mathbf{U}(k) &= (\mathbf{U}_{PG}^T(k), \mathbf{U}_{TLCN}^T(k))^T, \\ \mathbf{X}(k) &= (\mathbf{X}_{PG}^T(k), \mathbf{X}_{TLCN}^T(k))^T, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

We compare MCS and RESTART guided by the DNLV. The TLCN considers $t^- = 10$ [ms] and $t^+ = 40$ [ms] for all links, and timeouts of 80 [ms]. As in the previous case study, we consider a mission time of 100 [h] and a timestep $\Delta t = 15$ min. We increase the allocated computational time to 10 [h] to account for the greater model complexity of the IP&TLCN compared to the IEEE14 of the previous case study. RESTART parameters are set as in the previous section, with the thresholds of Table 5. In the DNLV, we assign source-targets for each network: for the power grid, we assign generators as sources and customers as targets (as in the previous case study), whereas, for the TLCN, we assign the SMDs as sources and the CC as target.

Table 6 compares the efficiency for the third and the fourth thresholds, using the DNLV. It can be seen that, as in the previous case study, RESTART is the method that best allocates computational resources for sampling high importance zones. The efficiency is lower than in the previous case, which suggests that the thresholds were placed conservatively (i.e., low).

In Fig. 10, we visualize the impact of disconnecting a low centrality TLC link (i.e., (1, 5)), yielding a slight increase on the DNLV. On the other hand, Fig. 11 shows the case of disconnection of a high centrality TLC link (i.e., (2, 7)), producing a larger DNLV increase and, thus, underlying the relevance of the scenario. These properties are similar to the ones of the previous case study, confirming that RESTART can effectively guide the scenario generation for the IP&TLCN using the DNLV.

Table 5
Threshold values considered for the IF in the IP&TLCN.

IF	Thresholds
ϕ	{0.0, 2.44, 2.72, 3.57, 4.99, 6.97, 9.51, 12.62, 16.30}

Table 6
Performance comparison between MCS and RESTART for the IP&TLC case.

IF	MCS		RESTART	
	$n_{sim} = 32180$		$n_{sim} = 29122$	
ϕ	$\xi(T_3)$	$\xi(T_4)$	$\xi(T_3)$	$\xi(T_4)$
	0.0124	0.001	0.6867	0.4321

Fig. 10. Disconnection of a low importance TLCN link and its impact in the DNLV.

Fig. 11. Disconnection of a high importance TLCN link and its impact in the DNLV.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we have considered the rare event simulation method RESTART for generating relevant CPS scenarios within the context of CRA. We have tailored the method by introducing a novel dynamic IF that accounts for the relevance of the states of the components of the CPS to guide the simulation of the scenarios so as to favor conditions leading to CPS failure. The IF combines a flow centrality metric of the components in the CPS network with their susceptibility to failure. The results of the application of the proposed method to two case studies regarding the IEEE14 power grid and an IP&TLC network confirm that: (1) the exploration of RESTART depends strongly on the selected IF, (2) typical vulnerability metrics (PGM, number of down components, ENS percentage) fail to efficiently guide RESTART in generating relevant scenarios towards CPS failure, and (3) the novel IF proposed in this paper is shown effective with respect to the other approaches by means of an exploration efficiency metric. Since RESTART does not impose constraints on the dynamics of the system, this method can be extended to other applications without major adaptations. Future work will consist in post-processing the generated scenarios for performing the CRA of CPSs.

List of acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence	LS	Line Sampling
BBM	Black-Box Model	MCS	Monte Carlo Simulation
CC	Control Center	OPF	Optimal Power Flow
CE	Cross-Entropy	PF	Power Flow
CPS	Cyber-Physical System	PGM	Power Generation Mismatch
CRA	Computational Risk Assessment	PMU	Phasor Measurement Unit
DNV	Dynamic Network-level Vulnerability	RESTART	Repetitive Simulation Trials After Reaching Thresholds
ENS	Energy Not Supplied	SAIFI	System Average Interruption Frequency Index
GBM	Grey-Box Model	SMD	Smart Monitoring Device
IF	Importance Function	SS	Subset Simulation
IP&TLC	Integrated Power and Telecommunication	TLCN	Telecommunication Network
IS	Importance Sampling	WBM	White-Box Model

List of symbols

k	Simulation instant	\mathcal{C}	Set of power grid customers
t_k	Simulation time at instant k	\mathcal{G}	Set of power grid generators
$t_{\text{day}}(k)$	Time of the day at instant k	\mathcal{L}	Set of power grid lines
Δt	Simulation time step	\mathcal{T}	Set of power grid transformers
n_x	Number of state variables	$\mathbf{E}_{\text{PG}}(k)$	Vector of power grid uncontrolled inputs
$n_{x,j}$	Number of state variables of the j -th component	$\mathbf{U}_{\text{PG}}(k)$	Vector of power grid-controlled inputs
n_e	Number of uncontrolled inputs	$\mathbf{A}_{\text{PG}}(k)$	Vector of power grid continuous variables
$n_{e,j}$	Number of uncontrolled inputs of the j -th component	$\mathbf{II}_{\text{PG}}(k)$	Vector of power grid discrete variables
n_u	Number of controlled inputs	$\mathbf{X}_{\text{PG}}(k)$	Power grid state vector
$n_{u,j}$	Number of controlled inputs of the j -th component	$\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{Gen}}(k)$	Vector of generators statuses
$\mathbf{X}(k)$	State vector	$\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{Line}}(k)$	Vector of line statuses
$\mathbf{E}(k)$	Uncontrolled inputs	$\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{Trafo}}(k)$	Vector of transformers statuses
$\mathbf{U}(k)$	Controlled inputs	$\mathbf{v}_{z,\text{gen}}(k)$	Vector of generators voltages angles
$\mathbf{A}(k)$	Continuous process variables	$\mathbf{p}_{g,\text{gen}}(k)$	Vector of generators active power setpoints
$\mathbf{II}(k)$	Discrete process variables	$\mathbf{v}_{m,\text{gen}}(k)$	Vector of generators voltages magnitudes
$\mathbf{F}(\cdot)$	State-transition function	$\mathbf{v}_{m,\text{sc}}(k)$	Vector of synchronous condenser voltage magnitudes
$\mathbf{X}_j(k)$	State vector of the j -th component	$\mathbf{p}_d(k)$	Vector of delivered active power demands
$\mathbf{X}_{(n)}$	n -th state vector in an ordered dataset	$\mathbf{q}_d(k)$	Vector of delivered reactive power demands
$\mathbf{x}_j^{+(l)}$	Maximum rating of the l -th state variable of component j	$\mathbf{p}_g(k)$	Vector of generated active power
$\mathbf{E}_j(k)$	Uncontrolled inputs of the j -th component	$\mathbf{q}_g(k)$	Vector of generated reactive power

(continued on next page)

(continued)

$\mathbf{U}_j(k)$	Controlled inputs of the j -th component	$\mathbf{v}_m(k)$	Vector of voltage magnitudes
Ω	State-space domain	$\mathbf{v}_\angle(k)$	Vector of voltage angles
$I_j^{(s-t)}$	Flow across component j induced by s and t	$\mathbf{S}(k)$	Vector of complex power generation
c_j	Centrality of the j -th component	$\bar{\mathbf{S}}(k)$	Vector of complex power generation in normal conditions
$s_j(k)$	Susceptibility of the j -th component	$\mathbf{E}_{\text{TLCN}}(k)$	Vector of TLCN uncontrolled inputs
$v_j(k)$	Weighted susceptibility of the j -th component	$\mathbf{U}_{\text{TLCN}}(k)$	Vector of TLCN controlled inputs
$\mathbb{V}(k)$	Dynamic Network-level Vulnerability	$\mathbf{U}_{\text{TLCN}}^l$	Bottom-up TLCN packet
$\phi(\cdot)$	Importance Function	$\mathbf{U}_{\text{TLCN}}^t(k)$	Top-down TLCN packet
C_i	Importance region i	$\mathbf{X}_{\text{TLCN}}(k)$	TLCN state vector
T_i^ϕ	Threshold that defines C_i in the range of ϕ	$\Psi(\cdot)$	TLCN transmission function
ΔC_i	Importance region between C_i and C_{i-1}	$t_d(\cdot)$	Time-dependent TLC link time delay
R_i	Retrials associated with C_i	\mathcal{P}_{ab}	TLC path between a and b
$\xi_\phi(\cdot)$	Exploration efficiency of ϕ	$T_d(\cdot)$	Total time delay
$\mathcal{D}_\mathcal{M}$	Dataset generated using method \mathcal{M}	p_d^a	Disconnection probability of TLC node
m	Number of thresholds	p_d^e	Disconnection probability of TLC link
$\bar{\mathbf{p}}_d(k)$	Vector of active power demands	$\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{node}}(k)$	Vector of TLC node statuses
$\bar{\mathbf{q}}_d(k)$	Vector of reactive power demands	$\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\text{link}}(k)$	Vector of TLC link statuses
\mathcal{B}	Set of power grid buses		

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Juan-Pablo Futalef: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Francesco Di Maio:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Enrico Zio:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Juan-Pablo Futalef reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge the funding received from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement GREYDIENT No 955393.

Appendix A. Centrality and susceptibility metrics

For completion, this Appendix recalls the concept of vulnerability and provides brief details on centrality and susceptibility metrics, with some examples of application.

Vulnerability has been coined in the literature to highlight those components in a complex network that, when disrupted, cause noticeable disturbances to the overall system [23]. Currently, there is no consensus on the most appropriate approach to conduct a vulnerability assessment, although analytical and simulation-based methods have been highlighted as major approaches [1,10]. Analytical solutions are faster and explainable, although they tackle simplified versions of the problem. Simulations, instead, are slower and require post-processing, though they can be more faithfully representative of the real system.

Centrality metrics are analytical approaches widely used for vulnerability assessment as they quantify the importance of elements in a network (vertices and links) according to a specific criterion [15]. Well-known centrality metrics include Degree Centrality, Betweenness Centrality (BC) and Closeness Centrality (CC). Specifically, BC is representative of the system function as it quantifies the average number of shortest paths passing through each node or link; however, since not all networks function based on shortest paths, new variants were introduced inspired by electrical network analysis, such as Current Flow BC (CF-BC) and Current Flow CC (CF-CC) [25].

While critical components are a primary focus, the combined failure of less critical components might be as disruptive as the former. By highlighting such less critical components, analytical methods can help guide detailed simulations and serve as informed exploration, thereby saving computational resources. For example, simulating scenarios where a critical component rarely fails might waste computational resources; instead, focusing on less critical components with higher failure chances can reveal unexpected configurations that lead to system failure.

The susceptibility of a component is a quantification of its degree of exposition to a threat or hazard: the more(less) susceptible a component, the more(less) the chances it fails. Component stress can be adopted as a dynamic measure of susceptibility as it represents its usage with respect to adequate ranges of operation, such as those provided by manufacturers, regulations, or physical laws, along a dynamic scenario. Stress is versatile since it can be adopted in most (if not all) domains. For instance, in the electrical domain, any electrical device or machine operates within well-defined voltage and current ranges. In the telecommunication domain, the communication latency among devices must be lower than a timeout setting. The same is true for other domains.

To illustrate the application of the metrics, consider the simple power grid example in Fig. 12a, where a single power source supplies power to five loads, and the transformer separates between high and low voltage zones. From Fig. 12a, evidently, interrupting the path between buses 0 and 1 will disconnect the power supply from the network. As a result, the power supply, the transformer, and buses 0 and 1 are the most critical components. In Fig. 12b, we map the power grid into a graph and compute the CF-BC considering the power supply (node 7) as the source, and the loads (nodes 8 to 12) as the targets. The CF-BC effectively highlights the critical nodes and links identified above. However, we observe that the nodes that represent the buses have high centrality as well, ranging from ~ 0.55 to ~ 0.7 ; this is relevant since removing them will cause line disconnections that act as current paths. Node 6 also shows high importance given the two outgoing lines (6, 5) and (6,4) that split the flows.

(a) Simple power grid diagram

(b) Map of the simple power grid into a graph and the obtained CFBC considering source {7} and targets {8, 9, 10, 11, 12}

Fig. 12. Demonstration of the mapping process of a simple power grid to its graph equivalent and the calculation of the CF-BC.

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